

Artificial Intelligence Based Psychological Detection of HTP Drawings

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Abstract. Art therapy gives therapists insight into unconscious emotions and thoughts of patients, often through non-verbal means. The House-Tree-Person (HTP) test is one of the oldest and most valued forms of art therapy, specifically in diagnosing mental disorders among children. However, it is usually hampered by subjectivity and the amount of time required for evaluation. Recent developments in artificial intelligence (AI) hence provide an opportunity to address such issues, enabling faster and more objective assessments. This research investigates how AI can further improve the analysis of HTP drawings for the detection of psychological disorders, particularly anxiety and depression in children. We utilised advanced data augmentation methods and fine-tuned deep learning models, such as VGG16, which achieved 97% accuracy in feature extraction. These features were then used to train machine learning models to assess psychological states, achieving significant accuracy. Among the models, the SVM model was most effective for detecting depression with 79% accuracy, and Random Forest showed the best results for anxiety detection with an accuracy of 68%. These findings suggest that integrating AI into the analysis of HTP tests can greatly reduce subjectivity and enhance the diagnostic process, leading to quicker and more reliable identification of psychological conditions in children.

Keywords: Art therapy · Artificial Intelligence · Explainable AI · Transfer Learning · Deep Learning · Data Augmentation

1 Introduction

Psychological disorders, such as anxiety and depression, significantly impact daily life and are often rooted in childhood experiences, genetics, or trauma. Art therapy, an established method for analysing these disorders, leverages artwork as a form of nonverbal communication between patients and therapists [1, 2]. Through art, individuals can convey unconscious thoughts and emotions, which is particularly valuable in assessing children or trauma survivors who struggle with verbal expression [3]. Among various art therapy techniques, the HTP test, developed by John Buck [8], is widely used to assess personality traits, family dynamics, and psychological conditions [6, 5].

Despite its popularity, the HTP test has inherent limitations, including time-consuming evaluations and subjective interpretations by therapists [9]. These challenges require improvements in the objectivity and efficiency of evaluations. With the growing integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare, AI models offer a promising avenue to automate and improve the analysis of HTP drawings. By reducing human error and expediting assessments, AI has the potential to significantly improve mental health diagnostics.

This research investigates the application of machine learning algorithms to analyse HTP drawings, specifically targeting the detection of anxiety and depression in children. The key contributions of this work are:

- Implementing enhanced labelling and annotation tools to minimise classification errors in HTP images drawn by children with limited motor skills.
- Addressing dataset imbalance by employing an advanced data augmentation approach to improve model robustness.
- Comparing the performance of several pre-trained and fine-tuned CNN models to identify the most effective model for feature extraction and classification of HTP drawings.
- Utilising advanced Explainable AI techniques, such as Grad-CAM, to interpret the decision-making processes of deep learning models during feature extraction.
- Evaluating the performance of multiple machine learning models trained on extracted features for detecting depression and anxiety scores in HTP images, as assessed by psychologists.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 reviews related work; Section 3 outlines the proposed methodology; Section 4 details the design specifications; Section 5 discusses model implementation; Section 6 presents results and evaluation, and Section 7 concludes the research.

2 Related Work

The HTP technique provides valuable psychological insights but is largely reliant on subjective therapist analysis [9]. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a promising solution to enhance the objectivity and efficiency of HTP analysis.

Kim et al. [9] first applied AI to HTP analysis, employing a three-step process involving object classification, psychological feature detection, and caption generation. Due to dataset limitations, only house and tree drawings were used, achieving 70% accuracy with the ResNet50 model.

Pan et al. [11] proposed an approach involving feature extraction and image classification using a dataset from the College of Control Science and Engineering at the China University of Petroleum. Their SVM-FEA model achieved an accuracy of 93%, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining feature extraction with machine learning techniques.

Salar et al. [10] utilised data from Istanbul Bilgi University and QuickDraw¹,

¹ QuickDraw!: <https://quickdraw.withgoogle.com/data>

applying the ResNet152 model and achieving 67% accuracy. Data augmentation was employed to address dataset limitations and improve model robustness. Lee et al. [4] focused on object detection in HTP analysis, using a dataset from the Goyang City Datathon². They compared several models, with Faster R-CNN achieving up to 95% accuracy on drawings of houses, trees, and people.

Author	Dataset Source	Model	Accuracy
Kim et. al. [9]	Google Image Data	CNN (ResNet50)	70%
Pan et. al. [11]	College of Control Science and Engineering China University of Petroleum	SVM-FEA	93%
Salar et. al. [10]	Istanbul Bilgi University & QuickDraw	CNN (ResNet152)	67%
Lee et. al. [4]	Goyang City Datathon	CNN (YOLOv5, Efficient-Det, SSD, Faster R-CNN)	House (Faster R-CNN) 95%, Tree (Faster R-CNN) 92%, Person (Faster R-CNN) 95%

Table 1. Chronological Ordered Comparative Analysis of the Psychological Disorder Detection by The HTP Test Drawings

Table 1 summaries AI-based projects analysing House-Tree-Person (HTP) drawings for detecting children’s mental health disorders like depression and anxiety. Although the HTP test dates back to the 1950s [8], research on the use of artificial intelligence technologies with HTP analysis remains quite limited. Existing studies demonstrate various gaps in the field. Projects such as Kim et al. (2021) [9] and Lee et al. (2024) [4] rely on datasets that have not been evaluated by professionals, which causes lower psychological validity and reliability, whereas studies such as Pan et al. (2022) [11] and Salar et al. (2023) [10] use datasets collected and analysed by experts but face performance challenges due to small number of data. Furthermore, the literature review emphasises the significance of improving project performance and reliability by using more carefully selected model parameters, models and steps so that AI assisted HTP analysis can contribute to timely and accurate mental health assessments for children.

3 Methodology

This section addresses dataset definition, data pre-processing, data augmentation, feature extraction and deep learning models. Figure 1 illustrates the proposed flowchart for the AI-based psychological detection by using HTP test drawings. This project consists of three main parts: Image Classification, Feature Extraction and Psychological Detection. In the first stage, Image Classification, the HTP drawings manually labelled on Label Studio. Secondly, Feature Extraction is performed using pre-trained deep learning models to extract key structural elements from house, tree, person drawings. Finally, the specified features are used to train machine learning algorithms that can detect psychological symptoms.

² Goyang City Datathon: <http://datathon.smilework.kr/>

Fig. 1. Project Structure

3.1 Data Analysis and Preprocessing

Based on the literature review, it is evident that the dataset for this project, aimed at detecting depression and anxiety through HTP test drawings using AI models, should be created under expert supervision to ensure its reliability and relevance. Therefore, the "HTP Images" dataset, developed by psychologists at Istanbul Bilgi University's Faculty of Psychology, was selected for this study, with appropriate ethical approvals obtained [10]. The dataset was collected with parental consent from child patients, under the guidance of psychologists from the Psychology Department. The children were asked to draw houses, trees, and people, and the resulting drawings were subsequently evaluated. Depression and anxiety scores were assigned by psychologists using the Child Behaviour Checklist³ as a reference.

Figure 2 illustrates sample house, tree, and person drawings from the HTP dataset, consisting of 450 unlabelled drawings from 83 children, which were converted from PDF to JPG format for ease of analysis and model training.

³ Child Behaviour Checklist: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Child_Behavior_Checklist

Fig. 2. HTP Images Dataset Samples

A detailed exploratory data analysis was performed by using all of these data to better understand the overall dataset structure. This analysis gave useful insights and guided the methods that were chosen for this study. The dataset consists of 53% male and 47% female participants, indicating a balanced gender distribution, which mitigates concerns regarding gender bias. The age range of the children is between 4 and 16 years, making the dataset appropriate for analysing children’s psychological states through the HTP test.

Following the dataset analysis, preprocessing steps such as resizing and normalising were applied to ensure uniformity across the images, standardising them to a resolution of 224x224 pixels. These preprocessing steps were essential for optimising the dataset for subsequent AI model training.

3.2 Image Classification Approach

The unlabelled HTP dataset, consisting of drawings of houses, trees, and people, posed a challenge for AI model, considering the AI models require accurately annotated data to achieve most reliable performance. Given the ethical necessity of certain reliability in child psychology applications, reducing the labelling errors was one of the most important aims in this research. To address this, manual labelling was performed to categorise the images into three classes: house, tree, and person, ensuring the accuracy crucial for child psychology applications, in contrast to several previous studies that relied heavily on automated annotation. Label Studio⁴, an open-source data labelling tool, was used to achieve uniform and reliable labelling of the drawing data. The image classification process began by defining the labels to be used, followed by importing the dataset into the project. Following this step, each image was subsequently labelled manually. Thanks to this approach, each drawing was classified into the correct class, also it allowed us to find and eliminate unnecessary sketches, incomplete drawings, and pages with no relevant content.

After classification, the images were exported in COCO format, which included image files along with a JSON file containing labels and object coordinates. Non-relevant drawings were removed, and blank pages were trimmed, resulting in a final dataset of 390 labelled images. This edited dataset provided

⁴ Label Studio: <https://labelstud.io>

an effective foundation to train the feature extraction model and understand key metrics in the drawings more effectively.

3.3 Feature Extraction Methods

The next phase of the project involved extracting features from the HTP test drawings. This step was crucial, as a thorough analysis of these features enabled the models to accurately differentiate between house, tree, and person drawings.

Data Augmentation To address the limited size of the dataset, a data augmentation strategy was implemented to expand the training data for the proposed models. The QuickDraw⁵ dataset, a drawing game developed by Google containing millions of drawings across 345 categories [10], was used in this process. Since the QuickDraw dataset did not include the "Person" category, 500 drawings from each of the "Face" category were utilised as a substitute. Additionally, 500 images from the "House" and "Tree" categories were selected using the QuickDraw Python library. Figure 3 illustrates the category distribution in the dataset before and after data augmentation, demonstrating the more balanced distribution achieved through this approach.

Fig. 3. Distribution of Images by Category: Before and After

Table 2 provides information about the structure of the dataset used for the feature extraction part after all these data augmentation steps.

3.4 Deep Learning Models for Feature Extraction

In this study, several deep learning models were employed to extract features from HTP drawings, specifically ResNet50, VGG16, and EfficientNet, each pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset:

⁵ QuickDraw!: <https://quickdraw.withgoogle.com/data>

Data Source	House	Tree	Person
HTP Images Data	87	78	225
Quick Draw! Data	500	500	500

Table 2. Feature Extraction Dataset Distribution

- **ResNet50:** ResNet50 is a 50-layer convolutional neural network (CNN) that has been extensively used in disease detection projects due to its high accuracy in recognising complex image patterns. As highlighted by Kim et al. [9], ResNet50 uses residual and skip connections to effectively learn from data, addressing common challenges in deep learning.
- **VGG16:** The VGG16 model, a 16-layer CNN, is well-suited for capturing intricate details and patterns, which is essential when analysing children’s drawings, such as those in HTP tests. Although VGG16 has not been widely applied to HTP images in prior research, its ability to process small, complex details makes it a suitable choice for this study.
- **EfficientNet:** Developed by Google Brain, EfficientNet employs a balanced scaling strategy to simultaneously optimise model depth, width, and resolution. This balanced approach enhances the model’s efficiency, making it well-suited for the complex features found in children’s HTP drawings.

3.5 Psychological Detection Methods

Several machine learning models were utilised in this study to assess anxiety and depression based on features extracted from HTP drawings:

- **Random Forest:** This approach operates as an ensemble of decision trees, each trained using random subsets of the dataset features, to predict anxiety and depression levels.
- **Decision Tree:** Decision Tree classifiers were used to segment the dataset based on the most relevant features, providing a straightforward classification method for psychological state detection.
- **Gaussian Naive Bayes:** This model employs Bayes’ Theorem to calculate the posterior probability for each class based on the input features. It was selected for its simplicity and efficiency, particularly in handling large datasets.
- **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** SVM was employed due to its simple structure and speed, which proved effective in identifying the hyperplane that best separates the data points. Previous studies, such as [11], have successfully used SVM for various health-related AI applications.
- **Logistic Regression:** Logistic Regression was applied as a binary classification model due to its effectiveness in similar disease detection tasks. Its simplicity and efficiency made it suitable for benchmarking against other proposed models on the HTP dataset.

4 Implementation

4.1 Feature Extraction

Following data preprocessing, augmentation, and image classification, feature extraction was performed. To address class imbalance, class weights were applied during model training. The labels in the "feature extraction" dataset (comprising original and QuickDraw images) were categorical—house, tree, and person—and were encoded as numerical values (0, 1, 2) using LabelEncoder.

Three pre-trained models—ResNet50, VGG16, and EfficientNet—were chosen based on their success in image classification tasks. These models were implemented using Keras and TensorFlow, with variations in the base model architecture. The architecture included a Flatten layer, followed by Dense layers with 1024, 256, and 64 units, and a softmax output layer for the three classes. Figure 4 shows the general architecture of the models, including additional layers.

Fig. 4. Base Model Architecture

Fine-tuning involved setting only the last 10 layers as trainable. The models were trained using the Adam optimiser with a low learning rate of $1e-5$ to minimise overfitting and prevent the propagation of incorrect predictions. Training was conducted for 10 epochs using an 80%-20% train-test split, incorporating class weights throughout. The best-performing model was saved for subsequent use.

4.2 Psychological Detection

The dataset for psychological detection was restructured using the best-performing model. The "HTP Images" dataset, labelled by psychologists, was organised into "Anxiety" and "Depression" folders, each containing "non_anxious/anxious" and "non_depressed/depressed" subfolders based on score thresholds (6 for anxiety, 4 for depression). Feature extraction was performed using the saved model, and class weights were used to address data imbalance. The "get_features" function was employed to resize, convert, and normalise the images, producing feature vectors.

The dataset was split into 80% training and 20% testing sets using the "ml_models" function. Random Forest was used with 300 estimators, SVM employed a linear kernel, and Logistic Regression was optimised over 1000 iterations.

5 Evaluation

5.1 Feature Extraction

Feature extraction is critical for the success of subsequent psychological detection steps. The performance of the ResNet50, VGG16, and EfficientNet models was evaluated using the metrics specified in Section 3.

The ResNet50 model achieved an accuracy of 89%, with a precision of 91%, recall of 89%, and an F1-score of 89%, demonstrating its effectiveness in extracting meaningful features from HTP drawings.

The pre-trained VGG16 model outperformed ResNet50, achieving 97% for accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, highlighting its strong capability in classifying drawings as house, tree, or person. Detailed performance metrics for VGG16 are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. VGG16 Model Performance Metrics

EfficientNet is the last model that has been trained and tested for the task of extracting the image features. The model, which showed a very low accuracy rate of 32%, was insufficient to understand the important features of house, tree and person drawings.

The graphs of the accuracy and loss rates achieved by the three models analysed in detail compared to the epochs in which they were trained are as shown in Figure 6. The results show that EfficientNet performed poorly in analysing the important characteristics of the images. It produced many errors while classifying house, tree, and person drawings, which caused a high rate of incorrect classifications based on the image characteristics.

The ResNet50 and VGG16 models achieved accuracy rates of 89% and 97%, respectively. VGG16 showed the most improvement, with increased accuracy and reduced loss over time, making it the best model for image feature extraction. Figure 7 shows the time spent running the models, which highlights the relationship between accuracy and processing time.

Fig. 6. Models' Accuracy and Loss by Epochs

Fig. 7. Training and Prediction Times of Deep Learning Models

Despite its longer processing time, the VGG16 model's complex calculations resulted in a more effective and advanced model. Figure 8 shows the features that the VGG16 model gives attention to decision-making. As can be understood from the image and performance metrics, the VGG16 model has shown a better performance due to being more sensitive to the details of drawings and more aware of their important features.

5.2 Psychological Detection

The psychological detection process began by analysing house, tree, and person drawings to identify depression and anxiety. Machine learning models were trained on the edited "Depression" dataset, with performance metrics shown in Table 3.

Fig. 8. VGG16 Grad-CAM

Machine Learning Models	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Random Forest	69%	72%	68%	72%
Decision Tree	60%	59%	59%	59%
Gaussian Naive Bayes	64%	69%	62%	69%
SVM	79%	79%	79%	79%
Logistic Regression	76%	77%	77%	77%

Table 3. Machine Learning Models' Performances for Depression Detection

The Random Forest model achieved an accuracy of 72%, with a precision of 69%, recall of 72%, and an F1 score of 68%. The Decision Tree model performed less effectively, with an accuracy of 59%. Gaussian Naive Bayes reached 69% accuracy, while the SVM model outperformed others with 79% accuracy across all metrics. Logistic Regression also performed well, achieving 77% accuracy. Overall, SVM was the most effective for detecting depression.

All models previously evaluated for depression detection were also tested for anxiety detection using the "Anxiety" dataset. Following feature extraction, the models were trained and their performance metrics are summarised in Table 4.

Machine Learning Models	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
Random Forest	74%	68%	61%	68%
Decision Tree	61%	62%	61%	62%
Gaussian Naive Bayes	49%	56%	49%	56%
SVM	66%	67%	66%	66%
Logistic Regression	62%	63%	62%	63%

Table 4. Machine Learning Models' Performances for Anxiety Detection

The Random Forest model for anxiety detection achieved 68% accuracy, with 74% precision, 68% recall, and 61% F1 score. The Decision Tree model followed, attaining 62% accuracy, 61% precision, 62% recall, and 61% F1 score. The Gaussian Naive Bayes model had lower performance, with 56% accuracy, 49% precision, and 56% recall. The SVM model achieved 66% accuracy, matching the Random Forest's performance with 66% precision and 67% recall. Finally, Logistic Regression attained 63% accuracy and 62% precision, but was less effective than Random Forest. Overall, both Random Forest and SVM models were effective, with Random Forest demonstrating the best performance.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

The HTP test is an invaluable art therapy technique for children, enabling therapists to assess drawings of houses, trees, and people to gain insights into family dynamics, personality traits, and social relationships. This project aims to enhance HTP test analysis by automating the psychological assessment process using AI. By using professionally collected and manually labelled dataset using Label Studio tool and advanced feature extraction tools using pre-trained and fine-tuned deep learning models, the VGG16 model achieved 97% accuracy in feature extraction. The Grad-CAM visualisation which is an Explainable AI method is used to reveal the regions of drawings that contributed most to model decision, which provides transparency on a sensitive psychological topic like this. The collected features enabled effective depression and anxiety detection, with SVM model achieving 79% accuracy in depression detection, while Random Forest reached 68% accuracy in anxiety detection.

Future research should focus on expanding the dataset with larger, labelled HTP images collected in professional environments, ensuring ethical considerations are met. Algorithm performance could be improved by incorporating new features, such as object size and quantity—elements that psychologists consider in HTP analysis. Addressing these aspects could provide deeper insights into children’s anxiety and depression, enabling earlier detection and intervention.

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